

Formal verification of critical PLC programs and neural network controllers at CERN

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*Contains joint work of several members and former members of the **BE-ICS group at CERN***

Roadmap

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- CERN has the biggest particle accelerator complex in the world and **many critical and complex industrial installations**

LHC
(Large Hadron Collider)

Access and
protection
systems

Cryogenics plants

Cooling and ventilation
systems

Superconducting magnet test benches

BE-ICS group in a nutshell

- “BE-ICS provides the **technology, frameworks, engineering** and CERN-wide **support** for systems and projects in all domains using standard **industrial control solutions**” <https://be-dep-ics.web.cern.ch>
- BE-ICS is in charge of the design and development of industrial **control** and **safety** systems

WinCCOA

Industrial PCs (FEC)

Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC)

CERN control centre

Cooling and ventilation systems

Superconducting magnet test benches

Cryogenics plants

Context – PLCs at CERN

- At CERN, more than 3000 **PLCs** (Programmable Logic Controllers) are installed to **control** and/or **protect** the installations

Example of PLC program

```
(* MODE MANAGER *)
IF NOT (#HLD AND #PHLD) THEN
  (* Forced Mode *)
  IF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
     #EMFoMoR AND NOT (#AuIhFoMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Software Local Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux) AND #EMSoftLDR AND NOT #AuIhFoMo THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := TRUE;

  (* Manual Mode *)
  ELSIF (#AuMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) AND
     #EMMoR AND NOT (#AuIhMo) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #MMoSt_aux := TRUE;
    #FoMoSt_aux := FALSE;
    #SoftLDSt_aux := FALSE;

  (* Auto Mode *)
  ELSIF (#MMoSt_aux AND (#EMAuMoR OR #EMAuMoR)) OR
     (#FoMoSt_aux AND #EMAuMoR) OR
     (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #EMAuMoR) OR
     (#MMoSt_aux AND #AuIhMo) OR
     (#FoMoSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
     (#SoftLDSt_aux AND #AuIhFoMo) OR
     NOT (#AuMoSt_aux OR #MMoSt_aux OR #FoMoSt_aux OR #SoftLDSt_aux) THEN

    #AuMoSt_aux := TRUE;
  END IF
END IF
```

Example of specification (ambiguous and incomplete)

Need to guarantee “complex” properties
 if **MMoSt and AuAuMoR** at any time before the end of the PLC cycle,
 then **AuMoSt** should be true at the end of the same PLC cycle

Formal verification
 (e.g. model checking)

Roadmap

Why formal verification?

- If “*Input1*”, “*Input2*”, “*Input3*” and “*Input4*” are **BOOL**, then we need to check $2^4 = 16$ combinations
- If they are **INT** (16-bit), then $2^{16 \cdot 4} \approx 1.8 \cdot 10^{19}$ combinations
- for large systems (many variables), such requirements **cannot** (practically) be checked by using testing techniques
- **Peer reviews** and **testing** can (normally) catch most of the “problems” (e.g. code bugs), but not the **corner cases**
 - **E.g. Ariane 5 rocket explosion** (more than 500 millions US\$ cost due to a software flaw in control software)

Solution: **Model checking**

What are Formal Methods?

Techniques based on **mathematics and formal logic (precise semantics)**

Graphical languages

Petri nets, automata, ...

e.g. **system model**
(model checking)

Textual languages

B-method, VDM, TLA+, ...

B-method

```

MACHINE
  Switch
SETS
  STATE = {closed, open}
VARIABLES
  state
INVARIANT
  state : STATE
INITIALISATION
  state := open
OPERATIONS
  toggle =
    IF state = open
    THEN
      state := closed
    ELSE
      state := open
    END ;
END
  
```

Mathematical languages

Temporal logic,
propositional logic, Z
notation, ...

e.g. **properties**
(model checking)

Temporal logic

$AG((a \wedge b) \rightarrow c)$

Propositional logic

$(A \rightarrow B) \vdash (\neg B \rightarrow \neg A)$

They can be used for **specification, verification, simulation, test case generation**, etc.

Where are Formal Methods being used?

Formal specification

COMPASS

Correctness, Modelling and Performance of Aerospace Systems

<http://www.compass-toolset.org>

Using **TLA+** to create a clear and concise specification, leading to a subsequent code reduction <https://cacm.acm.org/magazines/2015/4/184701-how-amazon-web-services-uses-formal-methods/fulltext>

Use of the formal specification language **VDM** to specify industrial applications

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/2879682_The_IFAD_VDM-SL_toolbox

Formal Verification of Critical Aerospace Software <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01184099/document>

Formal verification

Integration of their **static analyser** INFER into their **software development** process <https://www.inf.ed.ac.uk/teaching/courses/sp/2019/lecs/distefano-scaling-2019.pdf>

NASA AMES Robust Software Engineering group

<https://www.nasa.gov/isd-robust-software-engineering>

Use of the model checker SPIN to verify the model of a software

<http://spinroot.com/gerard/pdf/spin04.pdf>

Verification of **neural-network-based control** systems in non-towered airports to avoid collisions at landing

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356096882_Formal_Analysis_of_Neural_Network-Based_Systems_in_the_Aircraft_Domain

And many more ...

Why aren't Formal Methods widely used?

Pros	Cons
<i>Unambiguity</i> (well-defined semantics)	<i>High cost</i> (time)
<i>Precision</i> (e.g. software verification)	<i>Limitation of computational models</i> (state space explosion in model checking)
...	<i>Usability</i>

- Using formal methods is **more “expensive”** than traditional alternatives in engineering
- Real-life system models may be too large **to be handled by simulators or model checkers**
- We should **apply them when the cost of a failure is higher than the cost of using them** (tool support)

Formal methods and the standards (e.g. functional safety)

IEC 61508: Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems

Table A.1 – Software safety requirements specification

(See 7.2)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1a	Semi-formal methods	Table B.7	R	R	HR	HR
1b	Formal methods	B.2.2, C.2.4	---	R	R	HR
2	Forward traceability between the system safety requirements and the software safety requirements	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
3	Backward traceability between the safety requirements and the perceived safety needs	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
4	Computer-aided specification tools to support appropriate techniques/measures above	B.2.4	R	R	HR	HR

Table A.5 – Software design and development – software module testing and integration

(See 7.4.7 and 7.4.8)

Technique/Measure *		Ref.	SIL 1	SIL 2	SIL 3	SIL 4
1	Probabilistic testing	C.5.1	---	R	R	R
2	Dynamic analysis and testing	B.6.5 Table B.2	R	HR	HR	HR
3	Data recording and analysis	C.5.2	HR	HR	HR	HR
4	Functional and black box testing	B.5.1 B.5.2 Table B.3	HR	HR	HR	HR
5	Performance testing	Table B.6	R	R	HR	HR
6	Model based testing	C.5.27	R	R	HR	HR
7	Interface testing	C.5.3	R	R	HR	HR
8	Test management and automation tools	C.4.7	R	HR	HR	HR
9	Forward traceability between the software design specification and the module and integration test specifications	C.2.11	R	R	HR	HR
10	Formal verification	C.5.12	---	---	R	R

IEC 61511: Functional safety – Safety instrumented systems for the process industry sector

- several references to model checking. For example from IEC 61511-2:2016 Annex B:

“... specification should be implemented in the graphical language of the **model checking** workbench environment...”

Introduction to model checking (for PLC programs)

Given a **global model** of the system and a **formal property**, the model checking algorithm **checks exhaustively** that the model meets the property

Clarke and Emerson (1982) and Queille and Sifakis (1982)

Model Checking lectures
(Aachen university)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y5Hg4MvUXc4&list=PLwabKnOFhE38C0o6z_bhIF_uOUIbIDTjh

Property failed
Trace leading to the violation

Property OK

Was born for **hardware design**, today it is used extensively for **software verification** as well

PLCverif (for users)

The screenshot displays the PLCverif application interface. On the left, the Project Explorer shows a project structure with folders like 'output', 'src-gen', and 'Verification case...'. The main window shows the 'Verification backend' settings, where 'NuSMV' is selected in the 'Backend' dropdown menu. Below this, there are sections for 'Requirement', 'Requirement - advanced', 'Reporters', and 'Advanced settings'. The 'Verify' section contains a 'Verify!' button and a status area showing 'Last result: N/A', 'Last execution: N/A', and 'Last duration: N/A'. At the bottom, a table displays the output of the verification process.

OUTPUT BOOL	FC1.out1	false
OUTPUT BOOL	FC1.out2	false

The **complexity** of using formal methods **is hidden** by the PLCverif

Some references

Real case studies

 B. Fernández et al. “Applying model checking to industrial-sized PLC programs”. In *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7295624>

 B. Fernandez et al. “Applying model checking to critical PLC applications : An ITER case study” in *Proc. of the 17th ICALEPCS* <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2305319/files/thpha161.pdf>

 B. Fernandez et al. “Applying model checking to highly-configurable safety critical software: The SPS-PPS PLC program” in *Proc. of the 18th ICALEPCS* <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2809709/files/document.pdf>

 B. Fernandez et al. “Cause-and-Effect Matrix specifications for safety critical systems at CERN” in *Proc. of the 17th ICALEPCS* <https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/icalepcs2019/papers/mopha041.pdf>

Research activities

 Ignacio D. Lopez-Miguel et al. “Simplification of numeric variables for PLC model checking”. In *Proc. of the MEMOCODE '21* <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3487212.3487334>

 Milán Mondok. “Evaluating compositional verification options for PLCverif”. In *CERN internal note* https://cds.cern.ch/record/2780057/files/compositional_verification.pdf

 B. Fernández et al. “Modelling and formal verification of timing aspects in large PLC programs”. In *Proc. of IFAC World Congress'14* <http://cds.cern.ch/record/1956687/files/CERN-ACC-2014-0226.pdf>

 D. Darvas et al. “A formal specification method for PLC-based applications” in *Proc. of the 15th ICALEPCS* <https://accelconf.web.cern.ch/ICALEPCS2015/papers/wepqf091.pdf>

 Zsófia Ádám et al. “From Natural Language Requirements to the Verification of Programmable Logic Controllers: Integrating FRET into PLCverif”. In *NASA Formal Methods Symposium* https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-33170-1_21

 Mihály Dobos-Kovács. “Counterexample analysis of formal verification methods”. In *CERN internal note* https://cds.cern.ch/record/2779411/files/MihalyDobosKovacs_report.pdf

Roadmap

First steps

Context – CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research)

- Many applications of machine learning at CERN

Robotics

Data analysis of the physics experiments

Particle accelerators Operation and beam optimization

Industrial controls

Context – Neural-network-based controllers

Why NN-based controllers?

Tasks hard to specify

- Autonomous driving

[2]

Several rule exceptions

Computationally fast

- Matrix multiplication

Versatile

- Non-linearities
- No need to linearize

Only data needed

- No physical modelling required
- Collect data

But a failure in the controller can be fatal

[2] Pisarov, Jelena & Mester, Gyula. (2020). The Future of Autonomous Vehicles. FME Transactions. 49. 29-35. 10.5937/fme2101029P.

Context – Verification of neural-network-based controllers

Why verification of NNs?

- **Guaranteeing properties**

- **Explainability**

Robustness

Dangerous curve to the right

+ noise

Children crossing

Monotonicity

Safety

- **Is it possible** that a given situation ever occurs?
- **Is there a combination** of inputs that leads to a given output?

Reachability

Stability

Case study – LHC cooling towers controller

- Induced draft cooling towers (IDCTs)
- **Provide cold water** for different LHC subsystems (e.g. cryogenics, chillers, air handling units, etc.)
- **Control actions:**
 - **Mode selection:**
 1. Ventilation
 2. Showering
 3. Bypass
 - **Fan speed**
- **Control objective:**
 - Keep **outlet water temperature within strict limits**
 - Utilize **minimum amount of energy**

Case study – NN description

Initial non-conventional NN architecture

Hidden layers

- Feedforward NN with **ReLU** and **SoftMax** activation functions
- Developed and trained with **Python Keras**
- Automatically translated to S7-1200 Siemens PLC Structured Control Language (**SCL**)

Case study

Properties to be verified

Operational modes reachability

Do these inputs exist?

Fan speed constraint satisfaction

Monotonicity

Do $t_0 < t_1$ exist such that $s_0 > s_1$?

Softmax overflow

Robustness

They help to better understanding the NN

They represent problems

Approaches to verify these properties

Different methods were applied and compared:

1. **nenum**: an open-source **NN verification** tool for **ReLU** NNs from Stony Brook University
<https://github.com/stanleybak/nenum>
2. **PLCverif**: an open-source formal **verification tool** for **PLC programs** from CERN <https://gitlab.com/plcverif-oss>
3. **Z3**: an open-source **theorem prover** from Microsoft Research <https://github.com/Z3Prover/z3>
4. **Testing**: traditional testing techniques

nenum

NN design

PV

PLC source code

Executable

Ignacio D. Lopez-Miguel et al. “**Verification of Neural Networks Meets PLC Code: An LHC Cooling Tower Control System at CERN**”. In *EANN 2023: Engineering Applications of Neural Networks conference*
https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-34204-2_35

nnenum

Property encoding (vnnlib)

```
(declare-const X_0 Real)
(declare-const X_1 Real)
(declare-const X_2 Real)
(declare-const Y_0 Real)
(declare-const Y_1 Real)
(declare-const Y_2 Real)
(assert (>= X_0 20.0))
(assert (<= X_0 25.0))
(assert (>= X_1 23))
(assert (<= X_1 27))
(assert (>= X_2 8.0))
(assert (<= X_2 21.0))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_1))
(assert (>= Y_0 Y_2))
```

Inputs

Outputs

Range of the inputs:

$$25 \geq x_0 \geq 20$$

$$27 \geq x_1 \geq 23$$

$$21 \geq x_2 \geq 8$$

Property to verify:

$$y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2$$

It is possible that the selected mode is ventilation

Goal

Find an example that satisfies all conditions, i.e., a set of $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\}$ such that $(y_0 \geq y_1 \wedge y_0 \geq y_2)$

Execution

```
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work# python3 -m nnenum.nnenum sharedDocker/final/modes.onnx sharedDocker/final/modesReachability_0.vnnlib
Running in parallel with 16 processes
(0.1 sec) Q: 0, Sets: 0/1 (0.0%) ETA: - (expected 1 stars)
Pre-overapproximation simulation found a confirmed counterexample.
Unsafe Base Branch: (Mode: 0)
Total Stars: 1 (0 exact, 1 approx)
Runtime: 0.1 sec
Completed work frac: 1.0
Num Stars Copied Between Processes: 0
Num Lps During Enumeration: 0
Total Num Lps: 0
Result: network is UNSAFE with confirmed counterexample in result.cinput and result.coutput
Input: [22.5, 25.0, 14.5]
Output: [0.7701750993728638, -0.5644218325614929, -1.8442020416259766]
root@7d4848b3ea5f:/work#
```

Evidence

Pros:

- Very efficient
- Scalable

Cons:

- Limited to certain architectures
- No loops
- No complex properties

Roadmap

Conclusions (1)

- **Formal verification** (e.g. model checking) can be used **to verify critical software** (critical PLC programs)
- There are not commercial tools (yet) for PLC programs, this is why we developed **PLCverif**
- **PLCverif has been applied to many critical PLC programs** at CERN and outside CERN
- Still many **challenges**:
 - **State space explosion** problem (verification performance)
 - Properties **specification**
 - Automatic generation of models
 - **Counterexample analysis** (what do we do when we find a problem?)

Conclusions (2)

1. Important to verify neural networks in critical systems to:
 - guarantee properties such as robustness, stability, safety, etc.
 - have a better understanding of the behavior of the NN

Simulation.input1	Floating-point nu...	21.3	21.3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input2	Floating-point nu...	23.0	23.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Simulation.input3	Floating-point nu...	8.0	8.0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.fan_speed	Floating-point nu...	0.00262890317651313		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[0]	Floating-point nu...	6.01462636744791E-08		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[1]	Floating-point nu...	0.00348845387816139		<input type="checkbox"/>	
NN_Result_DB.modes[2]	Floating-point nu...	0.996511485975575		<input type="checkbox"/>	

2. We use **simulators** (e.g. Siemens PLCSIM advanced) to confirm the property violations (counterexamples)

3. We analyzed **different verification tools**

	performance	scalability	expressiveness	same types?	plug-and-play?
PLCverif	low	low	high	yes	yes
nnenum	very high	high	low	no	no
Z3	medium	medium	low	no	no
Testing	high	very low	medium	no	no

Ignacio D. Lopez-Miguel et al. "Verification of Neural Networks Meets PLC Code: An LHC Cooling Tower Control System at CERN". In EANN 2023: Engineering Applications of Neural Networks conference https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-34204-2_35

4. We have applied to a real **case study** for industrial controls at **CERN**

Future work

“Traditional” PLC-based controllers

NN-based controllers

Towards **reliable and safe control software**